

THE ROLE OF MULTILINGUALISM IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *Multilingualism has become an important aspect nowadays. In the past, several concepts and approaches for teaching language subjects have been developed, which are understood under the term multilingual didactics. The aim is to demonstrate the development of integrative multilingualism in learners by translating multilingual competences and language learning experiences into action in the language classroom. This article presents the results of empirical studies. Certain aspects of multilingualism are examined in a variety of ways in the classroom. It addresses the questions of what language teachers in German-speaking countries think about multilingual didactics, how they implement such concepts in the classroom and what support they receive in doing so. Based on the results, recommendations are formulated for the training and further training of language teachers, teaching and learning materials, further research and teaching practice.*

Keywords: *multilingualism, multilingual, codeswitching, monolingualism, bilingualism.*

РОЛЬ МНОГОЯЗЫЧИЯ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *Многоязычие в наши дни стало важным аспектом. В прошлом было разработано несколько концепций и подходов к преподаванию языковых предметов, которые понимаются под термином многоязычная дидактика. Цель состоит в том, чтобы продемонстрировать развитие интегративного многоязычия у учащихся путем воплощения многоязычных компетенций и опыта изучения языка в действия в языковом классе. В данной статье представлены результаты эмпирических исследований. Некоторые аспекты многоязычия рассматриваются в классе по-разному. В нем рассматриваются вопросы о том, что преподаватели языка в немецкоязычных странах думают о многоязычной дидактике, как они реализуют такие концепции в классе и какую поддержку они получают при этом. По результатам сформулированы рекомендации по подготовке и повышению квалификации преподавателей языка, учебно-методические материалы, дальнейшие исследования и педагогическая практика.*

Ключевые слова: *многоязычие, многоязычие, переключение кодов, монолингвизм, двуязычие.*

Introduction

The majority of immigrants in Germany are guest workers who grew up as a foreign population between 1950 and 1970. The number is just under three million. The main aim of this increase in Germany was the recruitment of foreign workers. The guest workers were a great help to the developing West German economy. In a narrower sense, monolingualism is neither logical nor phenomenal and cannot exist at all. This is why scholars disagree on whether or not boundaries exist between languages. Consequently, there are no clear statements on this because, firstly, it is not clear how many languages exist in the world at all; secondly, languages cannot simply be counted; thirdly, it is unclear where the boundary between monolingualism, bilingualism and

multilingualism lies. (Stötzel & Eitz, 2002)

Nowadays, teachers of all subjects and concepts have to deal with pupils who are multilingual. For example, migration backgrounds, bilingual homes and the languages of the countries of origin are the many causes of multilingualism and are characterized by the fact that an individual has more than one language, which enables him or her to satisfy written and/or oral communicative needs in everyday life in changing situations alternately in several languages. In order to take account of the multilingualism of today's pupils in language teaching, various concepts and approaches have been developed in recent years that can be summarized under the term multilingual didactics.

Multilingualism dispute

It can now be assumed whether multilingualism is observed as an important resource or vice versa. It is important that the topic is presented from two perspectives. A positive and a negative perspective. This chapter deals with the cause of multilingualism. Why is the topic seen in two ways? Why do some countries with a migrant background still have problems? Why are the languages of origin seen as a hindrance in the destination country? In the following, a distinction is made between two perspectives on multilingualism.

Positive aspects

The advocates of language policy regard multilingualism in society as mere recognition and they consider multilingualism instrumental as an important resource with great potential. Everyone has the innate ability to learn several languages. Language development takes place in the environment in which people live. That is why every person's language development must be encouraged. Prof. Dr. Tracy considers multilingualism to have great potential and has developed the topic of as follows: "Multilingualism is a great potential for our society and we should maintain it. In the globalized world, there are people who can act as language mediators and they can speak different languages flexibly. And that is of course a great resource[...]"(Tracy. 2014. p. 20) Nowadays there is a big debate within Germany as to whether or not multilingual immigrants harm the German language.

Moreover, all people on this planet have this ability, regardless of their age. This language diversity does not confuse the child at all. Most scientists, such as the scientist Ingrid Gogolin, consider this process to be language switching (codeswitching) and this is different from language mish-mash. The topic of language switching is discussed in more detail in chapter five. Gogolin mentioned the following about children's general language skills: "At the beginning of an educational career, i.e. when entering kindergarten or elementary school, it is of great importance that a child has age-appropriate general language skills. Language diagnostic instruments should therefore be aimed at finding out about such abilities." (Gogolin. 2005. p. 13) The methods available so far are outlined as language development and multilingualism is seen as a valid resource for all people. Multilingualism is the treasure and it develops or encourages people to be more intelligent. The negative aspect is presented first. In some newspapers, multilingualism is seen as a burden.

Negative aspects

Learning two or more languages at the same time represents slow language development. For some scientists, multilingualism is a disruptive factor. Opponents of multilingualism do not

consider the process of multilingualism to be normal. Bilingual children are under pressure and they are overwhelmed. In addition, multilingual children are confused when it comes to mastering several languages at the same time.

It is clear to see that most immigrants and refugees with a migration background have a bad reputation in Germany. This means that in most newspapers and magazines the topic is seen as a major conflict. The question arises as to why most people with a migrant background still have educational problems. For what reason are the immigrants' languages of origin seen as a hindrance? integration problem in Germany. Neither our language nor our culture as a whole are popular with a significant proportion of immigrants in Germany." (Kraus. 2018. p. 4)

Furthermore, the author of this article shows that the problem does not exist with some groups. For example, Germans have no problem with immigrants from EU countries, Chinese, Alevi, Syrian Christians, Iranian exiles and Muslims in general. Most of the above groups are successfully integrated linguistically. The problem lies with the conservative milieu. In other words, the problem has to do with the education of these people. It is clear that such people are not in a position to grow multilingually in society. In this context, multilingualism means that people assimilate primarily to the educational rules. But such people do not want to adapt to the situation. Therefore, in this article you will find factors that cause the process of multilingualism to fail. The factors can be the worst social conditions, no respect for teachers, physical and verbal violence against classmates and teachers, knife attacks, drugs, alcohol, etc. (Kraus. 2018. p.5)

Results

The results of the analysis are as follows. In order to start an effective multilingualism process, teachers need current teaching practice. Therefore, we provide the prerequisites for multilingualism didactics as well as the training and further training for teachers to use the first or second language in a relevant way in the classroom. In addition, multilingual pupils show active participation in the classroom. In teaching practice, we need active teachers in order to use the learners' activities in a variety of ways in the classroom. Teacher training and further training will be considered below. One goes assumes that the studies show that the majority of teachers of language subjects are not able to teach multilingually without appropriate initial and further training. Teachers should also be able to speak the learners' first and second languages well. In other words, the teachers themselves should be multilingual and they should design the lessons didactically. Didactically is meant when teachers prepare materials in class that activate multilingual learners in different areas. For example, when speaking, we can use authentic topics to activate several languages in different ways. Such tasks give the learners the impulse to pay attention to the different languages.

Summary

Languages are always changing. Historically, languages are seen to have disappeared over time. Monolingualism cannot exist. This means that languages are always interrelated.

All people can be raised to speak two or more languages from birth. Multilingualism can be a wonderful training for the brain. Most scientists find multilingualism to be a valid resource for any society. Multilingualism can have positive and negative aspects. Positive aspects are always considered normal and most people have the innate ability to grow and think multilingually.

In today's society, there are often factors that are viewed negatively. Some groups with a

migrant background are not able to be multilingual. In other words, they come with their languages of origin and they are conservative. In addition, such groups do not want to change and you always see conflicts at school.

There is a big difference between the term (codeswitching) and the language-mixing machine. In addition, people speak several languages at the same time in order to achieve their communicative goal.

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